

ISBE Infrastructure
for Systems Biology
Europe

Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe

Deliverable No: 13.2

Workshop report

Main/responsible author(s): Martijn J. Moné, Hans V. Westerhoff

Institution: VUA

Country: The Netherlands

Project ref. no.	INFRA-2012-2.2.4: 312455
Project title	ISBE – Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe
Nature of Deliverable	R= Report
Contractual date of delivery	Month 28
Actual date of delivery	Month 28
Deliverable number	D13.2
Deliverable title	Workshop report
Dissemination Level	PU
Number of pages	18 (excluding cover pages and ToC)
WP relevant to deliverable	WP13
Lead Participant	VUA
Author(s)	Martijn J. Moné, Hans V. Westerhoff, Garry L. Corthals, Babette Regierer, Jure Acimovic, and other partners
Project coordinator	Richard Kitney
EC Project Officer	Keji-Alex Adunmo

Project funded by the European Commission under the Seventh Framework program for Research and Technological Development

Dissemination level: PU = Public, RE = Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including Commission services), PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services), CO= Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)

Nature of Deliverable: P= Prototype, R= Report, D=Demonstrator, O = Other.

Table of Contents

- Introduction..... 1
- Background information to WP13 2
 - Objectives of WP13 2
 - Relationship to other work packages..... 2
- Expert and community meetings 3
 - 1. ISBE Business Case & Connections expert meeting 4
 - 2. NormSys/ISBE Workshop – Standards for Data and Model Exchange 7
 - 3. ISBE-CASyM joint Meeting on Education and Training 17

Introduction

ISBE connections should be formatted in ways that maximize the usefulness of the systems biology centres and, thereby, the infrastructure as a whole. They should greatly increase the yield and efficiency of European science and technology by enabling them to find, connect to, and engage with systems approaches and training thereof.

The ISBE WP13 aims to develop recommendations for what the connections in the infrastructure should comprise and how they should be structured in order to best serve the above purpose. WP13 defines the connectivity amongst ISBE nodes that enable European systems research and training activities to integrate and scale up. Connections include computer-only, computer-assisted and human-human interactions. Through ISBE, large systems biology-driven community efforts become feasible by connecting the expertise and resources of multiple different projects in past and present, and by enabling the new workforce to do so. This builds ISBE as a platform from which to launch large-scale integrative projects with high scientific and societal impact.

The partners of WP13 had finalised a draft proposal on the ISBE connections in month 15 (Deliverable D13.1, October 2013). In spring 2014, the steering committee initiated a structured process, led by WP11, towards drafting a Business Case by November 2014, which was subsequently concurred with by the consortium. The concepts and designs described in D13.1 provided a key part of the basis from which the delineation of the structure and functional coherence of the infrastructure as a whole was further being developed, back-to-back with the full ISBE consortium. WP13 partners engaged in drafting the Business Case and embedding the proposed connections therein. The contents of this draft document were used as the basis for obtaining comments and feedback from experts and the community.

Background information to WP13

Objectives of WP13

ISBE will consist of nodes and strong connections between these. Particularly Systems Biology needs to integrate various types of expertise that do not exist at a single location at the highest level of excellence. WP13 has the aim to make these connections seamless, ultrafast and user friendly. More specifically the objectives are:

- to define and design all possible connections between ISBE nodes that will promote European Systems Biology
- to design standard interfaces at ISBE nodes that enable computer assisted connecting
- to design ways in which large systems biology tasks can be partitioned over nodes and the results reintegrated

Relationship to other work packages

WP3 (Overall Infrastructure, Eligibility and Accessibility) will define the nodes and WP13 (Connections) will define the edges of the ISBE network. Together with WP4 (Data Generation), WP13 will define the technical interfaces for linking to the generation of data. WP13 will design the technical aspects of interfacing/data exchange during systems biology research projects (e.g. web services); WP5 (Community Building and Synergies) will define how the various organisations involved engage with each other before, and after, the active research happens. The insights gained by WP13 on the best ways of communicating, will serve WP7 (Strategy Vision and Advocacy) in developing further vision. WP11 (Funding, Governance and Legal) will mediate the discussions of how to implement the best ways of connecting research into actually funded research projects of research consortia. WP15 (Innovation, Impact and Exploitation) will explore possible connections with industry, where WP13 focuses on connections within ISBE and between ISBE and academic institutions.

Expert and community meetings

Expert and community feedback were collected from three separate meetings to ensure criticism and comments on all relevant aspects that relate to the ISBE connections.

The core meeting was a round-table discussion with world-leading experts in systems biology. Here the central document was a shorthand of the ISBE Business Case including Connections, which would provide the participants with a high-level understanding of the proposed overall infrastructure and, subsequently, to obtain critical feedback on the focus and operational dynamics of the infrastructure as a whole. This meeting was organised with the involvement of WP15 to include the essential aspect of connecting with industry.

As standardisation had been recognised as a pivotal aspect for a successful infrastructure, including optimal scientific connections, a separate public meeting on standards for data and model exchange, involving the systems biology standards community, was organised together with NormSys (community standards consortium in the field of computer modelling in systems biology – www.normsys.org), and ISBE WP2 and WP7.

To procure the presence and availability of sufficient world-leading experts as well as optimal coverage of the standards community, these two meetings were organised as satellites to the largest international congress on systems biology, the ICSB 2015 (Melbourne).

In addition, education and training had also been acknowledged as pivotal aspects of the infrastructure. Among other things, this will entail connecting through training to fields in which systems biology is anticipated to be applied, for example in systems medicine. Therefore we co-organised a joint meeting on education and training with the systems medicine consortium CASyM, involving the ERA-Net for Applied Systems Biology (ERASysAPP), and ISBE WP10. The meeting was held as a satellite to the Systems Biology and Systems Medicine School: Systems Biology and Systems Medicine – Precision Biotechnology and Therapies (Como, Italy).

1. ISBE Business Case & Connections expert meeting

Date:

15 September 2014

Venue:

Restaurant Silks, Crown Towers
8 Whiteman Street, Melbourne, Australia

Participants (in alphabetical order):

Garry Corthals (GC) - University of Turku, Finland
Stefan Hohmann (SH) - University of Gothenburg, Sweden
Michael Hucka (MH) - California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA, USA
Peter Hunter (PH) - Auckland Bioengineering Institute, New Zealand
Hiroaki Kitano (HK) - President and CEO of Sony Computer Science Laboratories & President of The Systems Biology Institute, Tokyo, Japan
Martijn J. Moné (MJM) - VU University Amsterdam, The Netherlands
Thomas Lemberger (TL) - Chief Editor of Molecular Systems Biology
Nicolas Le Novère (NLN) - Babraham Institute, Cambridge, UK
Hans Westerhoff (HW) - VU University Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Apologies sent:

Adriano Henney
Pamela Silver
Marc Wilkins

Appendix:

1 ISBE BC shorthand Melbourne.pdf

ISBE Business Case & Connections expert meeting, significant comments and feedback:

On ISBE offers:

- ISBE proposes to connect the storage of data to their integration, in a model-driven fashion. TL and NLN echo that this would be a novel, important and useful modus operandi. Consensus. TL underlines that ISBE may not always need to store data, but it could suffice to be able to link to it. PH, NLN, HW agree: combined integrated data and models.
- PH stresses that in addition to model storage and access, the provenance of model data is extremely important. Consensus.
- TL, agreeing with the previous notion, adds that it would be highly useful to link to the scientific resource as it was published (preferably in machine-readable fashion), as currently it is still very hard to come by; a lot of data is, for instance, just a jpeg or a text snippet in an minor, often inaccessible journal. Hence it would be good if it is linked to a newly published model.
- There was a short discussion on how to refer to services etc. in publishing, or citations to software. There is no agreement on how to resolve this, but overall consensus that it is an important issue that needs to be resolved
- HK: KEGG is gone now because of staffing issues. It is one of the most widely used online resources. TL suggests that ISBE could play an important role there, as well as in comparable situations.

- A common concern is that a lot of systems biology studies are predictive, yet often, for various reasons, the story ends there. A service for validation would be very helpful.

On multiscale modelling aspects:

- There was broad agreement that ISBE should put effort in facilitating multiscale approaches.
- ISBE should also take lead in multidisciplinary community efforts (e.g. involving mathematicians) to develop algorithms etc. to bridge multiscale.
- HK suggests drawing from and linking to the multidisciplinary research institution RIKEN.
- LNL suggests taking lesson from the modus operandi of the COMBINE consortium.

On addressing challenges:

- MH notes that to an outsider this scheme may suggest that there are already a lot of standards in SB. There are, however, little pervasive community standards.
- MH: There is an urgent need for the development of standards around how to encode multiscale models, including model reduction as part as the process. Agreement.
- TL suggests making a focused write-up on the need for infrastructure for multiscale modelling.

On governance:

- There was some misinterpretation regarding the governance structure as to the precise roles of the different entities; for example, it was not intuitive that national coordinators are mainly operating at the national level. This needs to be unambiguously explicated.
- The CIO should ideally be a full time position for several years, and, given the weight of the job, should not be an active scientist. Consensus.
- TL says it might be good to consider the EMBO model. Difference of opinion, but agreement that certain aspects are worthwhile. For instance, EMBO has a community-selected leader. This has its downsides, but they tend to represent the community very well, giving stakeholders the feeling of involvement. PH agrees.

Positioning ISBE by connecting to other fields:

- NLN notes that ISBE should underline its value for synthetic biology and bioengineering, as both have similar bottom-up challenges that the infrastructure appears to address. TL: indeed, this is a very important point, which should also be clear towards funders.
- MH: the same goes for systems medicine. Consensus, but the focus need not just be on healthcare per se, but on enabling research – hence facilitating systems medicine.
- HK suggests that in order to cater the demand part, one should take, for example, the healthcare agenda and assess the top issues that it wants to resolve, and argue how to supply filling-up of the scientific and technological gaps.
- More broadly, LNL suggests including a section on what will be done via ISBE that is not being done today.
- HK mentions that also brain and neurology research is in need of modelling support, with examples of CNS researchers regularly asking HK for aid in this.
- It would be good to liaise with Peer Bork as head of the ERC panel for systems biology to seek endorsement.
- Idem for connecting to the Virtual Physiological Human community (VPH) via Marco Viceconti.
- Idem for seeking recommendation from FPA (Pharma).

Open discussion and various remarks:

- MH states that it is important to think about how to deal with the service component of the infrastructure. For example in the area of stewardship, like for the SBML standard: although you can get some publications on a standard, most of the time work on them are not beneficial for one's career as a researcher. So one needs staff - and therefore career opportunities (no profs or postdocs) - for people who want to do that as a career.
- One service enticement modus operandi could be that service providers would be funded to have state-of-the-art equipment.
- GC mentions that Finland has something like that and offers to provide information on that.
- SH states that the same goes for Sweden (including software development), and offers to write a synopsis of that.
- MH suggests considering the working of scienceexchange.com on replication experiments and service provision; they also have an online platform to manage these matters.
- There was a short discussion on how much the business case needs to argue/defend the importance of systems biology, or whether that is accepted? TL suggests that it would be good anyhow to show data that systems biology is indeed still growing and high-impact, and that this is reinforced by quantitative data and quantitative assays etc. Hence, ISBE should more explicitly state how it provides experimental support.
- PH also supports this and says that early on there needs to be a statement on reproducibility. Standards flow from there. Consensus.
- It was remarked that "Future-proof operational needs of systems biology" should include sustainability and tech awareness
- NLN mentions that companies often approach the Brabham Institute for e.g. metabolomics or bioinformatics, and expects ISBE to similarly attract immediate customers related to predictive modelling.

2. NormSys/ISBE Workshop – Standards for Data and Model Exchange

Date:

18 September 2014

Venue:

University of Melbourne, School of Botany
G26 Seminar Room, Botany North Extension, Parkville, Australia

Participants:

About 25 in total.

Speakers & main discussion contributors (in alphabetical order):

Martin Golebiewski (MG) - HITS, Heidelberg, Germany (organiser)
Susanne Hollmann (SH) - University of Potsdam, Germany (organiser)
Mike Hucka (MH) - California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA, USA
Peter Hunter (PH) - Auckland Bioengineering Institute, New Zealand
Edda Klipp (EK) - Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany
Nicolas Le Novère (NLN) - Babraham Institute, Cambridge, UK
Thomas Lemberger (TL) - Chief Editor of Molecular Systems Biology
Huaiyu Mi (HM) - University of Southern California, Los Angeles, CA, USA
Martijn J. Moné (MJM) - VU Univ. Amsterdam, The Netherlands (organiser)
Chris J. Myers (CJM) - Univ. of Utah, Salt Lake City, UT, USA
David Nickerson (DN) - Auckland Bioengineering Institute, New Zealand
Andreas Posch (AP) - Siemens AG, Vienna, Austria
Babette Regierer (BR) - Wageningen Univ., NL / LifeGlimmer GmbH, Berlin, Germany (organiser)
Falk Schreiber (FS) - Univ. of Halle-Wittenberg, Germany & Monash Univ., Melbourne, Australia
Jacky Snoep (JS) - Stellenbosch University, South Africa
Natalie Stanford (NS) - Univ. of Manchester, UK
Hans Westerhoff (HW) - VU Univ. Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Appendices:

2 ISBE @Normsys-ISBE standards workshop - ISBE Connections - Moné.pdf
3 ISBE @Normsys-ISBE workshop - model-driven data management - Westerhoff.pdf

NormSys/ISBE Workshop – Standards for Data and Model Exchange in Systems Biology

Presentation synopses and relevant comments:

Setting the Standards for Data and Model Exchange (NormSys)

Martin Golebiewski

Susanne Hollmann

- New project NormSys “Norms and Standardisation for the exchange of models and data in systems biology research” funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy has the objectives to identify existing community standards, classify existing standards, compile a standards registry, develop a certification concept, evaluate standardisation options, drive community building and the transfer from grass-root activities to normative standards
- Special interest: synopsis and alignment between academic activities in standardisation and the ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology initiative
- How to bundle the efforts of standard developers, research initiatives and industry, publishers, funders, standardisation bodies?

Discussion:

- Question: What is the relation to BioSharing?
- Answer: A catalogue of standards already exists with BioSharing; NormSys is working more vertical for modelling, whereas BioSharing represents a more broad perspective. It is important to develop a strategy how these activities can be integrated.

Infrastructure for Systems Biology in Europe (ISBE)

Martijn Moné

Babette Regierer

- ISBE is currently in the strategy development phase how to build the infrastructure across Europe
- It is important to link to existing efforts and other research infrastructures
- Purpose of ISBE is to enable the access to resources and services to perform systems biology research
- The concept foresees a central office connecting to national contact points; the national contact points function as hubs connecting to other national institutions that are part of the infrastructure (“spokes-and-nodes” concept, similar to the ELIXIR concept)
- Standardisation is a core topic within ISBE

Discussion:

- Question: Will ISBE also be open to non-European collaborations?
- Answer: In principle yes, and very welcome

Data Standards and Publications

Integrating actionable data into publications

Thomas Lemberger

- Scientific publishing also plays an important role in standardisation
- Publishers face specific challenges to optimise the publishing process
- How to share information:
 - a) research data -> databases -> users
 - b) research data -> journals -> users
 - c) research data -> journals -> databases -> users
- Current challenges: data deposition, author checklist, data citation, source data
 - Data deposition: how to structure data? What information is important?
 - Author checklist: how to present data? Problem: figure caption, minimal information for figures must be given
 - Data citation: provide credit for data providers; how to allow citation of datasets/databases? Currently no general format available for primary data/referenced data; NISO-JATS is an open standard for representing full text articles in XML (will replace NLM-XML standard), and will support structured data citations according to the F11 Data Citation Principles
 - Source data: maybe we need a new way to present figures? One option could be to integrate the source data behind the figure, including metadata, coherent experimental units, enabling data-oriented searches, presentation of the data in the context of related data; description of the figure should also be more standardised so that they become searchable
- “Smart figures”: indexing etc. - “figures as packages”?
- Challenges: Avoid too much workload for the authors, minimise costs for publishers, demonstrable added value for users

Model-driven data management

Hans Westerhoff

- Standardization efforts should have an aim “to enable the life sciences to have useful output” (e.g. in precision medicine and biotechnology)
- Data management for systems biology / systems medicine should transform; data need to be integrated
- In life sciences we need to organise systems
- The systems (organisms) are often described in different “languages”
- Current situation: data explosion, knowledge implosion
- We should not look for single molecules, but for networks
- If we integrate data/information, we need to be sure about the aim
- Put data together in replica model (= virtual organism); data should be stored in the context of the model (mapped onto it)
- Data management for systems biology / systems medicine should be different: network accommodating
- Silicon / virtual organisms could serve as integrators
- Human metabolic map: successful example of such (static) data integration
- Silicon cell models: examples of such dynamic integrators (human glutathione, yeast, T. brucei, erythrocytes, E. coli, ...)
- Further integration: associate building blocks
- Standards for different organisms should be the same

Transparency and reproducibility in mathematical model construction, validation and publication in Systems Biology studies

Jacky Snoep

- Model construction needs to be transparent, allowing validation models should be reproducible
- JWS allows online simulation and links to scientific journals (e.g. FEBS Journal)
- ISA structure (ISA = Investigation Study and Assay)
- Conclusions:
 - All data used for model construction and validation should be made available when a mathematical model is published
 - Model construction / validation should be reproducible, i.e. make parameterisation scripts available
 - Technical curation of model and model description is important, e.g. make specifics for model simulation explicit

Discussion:

- JWS does not allow detailed review of models; but who does this technical validation of the models? TL wonders: would authors pay €100 more for validation of the models? If not the authors, who is paying for this validation?
- NLN states that for a successful strategy costs are to be added for model validation and data sharing in grants; this might be different for different countries with respect to how this will be handled
- EK proposes that, in addition to transparency and validation, model construction needs publishing guidelines

Modelling Standards

Reuse and large-scale integration of models

Edda Klipp

- Motivation: Exploding number of models, need for re-use of models and application to new questions, need to combine (the most appropriate) models for larger efforts, need to find data for parameter estimation
- Based on BioModels: retrieve, cluster, align sysbio models and data
- Challenge: automated comparison of models with different granularities and different biological concepts (semantic similarities)
- Problems in construction of complex models:
 - 1) model should be
 - plausible (subjective measure)
 - tested (has made sensible prediction)
 - in appropriate format (ODE, Boolean, statistical...)
 - parameterised
 - of appropriate coarseness
 - 2) data should be relevant and correct
 - retrieve data to parameterise larger models (referring to the organism of choice and the experimental conditions)
 - available data often have nothing in common with the models created to describe them
 - coverage of data is often quite different than needed for models to describe a certain process
 - meta-information is often missing
- Sustainability of tools: software tools, databases etc. are often created as part of student projects; they disappear/are not maintained; there is a need for continuity and integration into larger efforts
- For models and tools, there needs to be an easier way to publish them (for modellers) or supported through feasible funding mechanism; need for career paths

The Systems Biology Markup Language (SBML)

Mike Hucka

- Many tools for modelling available. Challenge: projects often need more than one tool, which, in turn, cannot interoperate
- SBML provides syntax and only limited semantics (important for machine readability)
- Raw models alone are insufficient; there is a need for standard schemes for machine-readable annotations (to identify entities, clarify mathematical semantics, link to other data resources, provide authorship and publication information); SBML supports to annotation schemes: SBO and MIRIAM

Discussion:

- SBML funding runs out in 2016. Infrastructural initiatives like ISBE could be a welcome solution for its long-term support.

Current directions for the Physiome standards (CellML, FieldML and BiosignalML)

Peter Hunter

1. Model curation

- Involved in model curation are: author, curator, journal editor, reviewers, readers

2. VPH model

- Establishment of the VPH Institute (Director: Marco Visconti, Sheffield)

- VPH-Share; online facility for medical simulation software, with links to clinical data; patient specific CellML parameters -> Open EHR -> VPH Share
 - VPH Share managed by a small group, mirrored at several sites around the world, tools for model curation, annotation and sharing, “drag and drop” modelling, models can be public or private, database includes multiple species (human, rat, mouse, horse, sheep, ...), database stores parameter sets and deals with the provenance of models and parameters, webservices for retrieving data and models or running simulations, provides links to bioinformatics – or systems biology - databases

Discussion:

- Question: what about ownership of the models? NLN: for BioModels there were only the developers of two models who needed to be contacted to provide free access to their models, so open access might not be an issue
- PH sees a clear link to ISBE for to provide such resource.
- Many discussants agree that multiscale is the next big challenge.
- Question MG: what about the sustainability of the databases, especially for multiscale models?
Answer PH: standards are needed for ways to connect the scales. Currently there are none
Response NLN: SED-ML is starting to support combined models
Comment CJM: Maybe so, but you do not want to have to jump between model runs. You want to run them in parallel, with an integrated solver. This can already be done in other existing (non-biological) solutions.

Modularity and reuse with CellML and the Physiome Repository

David Nickerson

- CellML:
 - simple structure
 - based on connected components
 - components can be abstract concepts by providing well-defined interfaces to other components
 - components encapsulate concepts by hiding details from other components
 - model reuse possible by importing components
 - model reuse encourages creation of model libraries
 - CellML does not distinguish between model as stand-alone entity or template
 - Possible to extract reusable generic (sub)models; useful to integrate as building blocks into larger models
 - How to manage modularity and reuse? E.g. recording of changes

Data Integration, Metadata Standards & Industry Requirements

Controlled metadata for model building, processing and enrichment

Nicolas Le Novère

- SBO = Systems Biology Ontology
- SBML and SBGN are associated with SBO terms; SBML and SBGN can be converted using SBO
- Allows conversion between modelling frameworks
- Standard formats can help to generate new research; example: kinetic models
- path2models: from pathways to models
 - provide pathways in a standard format
 - reuse existing pathway data to generate biochemically based models
 - provide starting points to build more quantitative models

Bachel et al. (2013)

- possible to combine different models and resources (logical models of individual signalling pathways, chemical kinetics models of individual metabolic pathways, flux balance analysis of whole genome reconstructions); produces a super-curated pathway in SBML
- >2600 species
- Large scale by automated processes and plug in what is available
- 142.000 models, 444M annotations -> cannot be done by hand
- RDF platform (resource description format): encodes information as a triplet; subject, predicate, object; format is unified for any kind of data; allows a precise identification of all 3 items; a sentence can be plugged in together, and all modules are precisely described
- Information is collected from all different types of sources and plugged together

Discussion:

- Question TL: is it possible to take a pattern in SBO and search SBML resources?
Answer NLN: has not been done yet, but that is a good idea

BioPAX - Biological Pathways Exchange

Huaiyu Mi

- BioPAX (www.biopax.org) is a standard exchange format to represent biological pathways at the molecular and cellular level
- To facilitate the exchange of pathway data; currently supported by most of the major pathway databases
- BioPAX relates to other standards
- Contains entities (3M classes) for pathway, interaction, physical entity; also contains “gene”, but it is more a concept than a physical entity
- Physical entities are subclasses, e.g. proteins, DNA, RNA, small molecules, DNA regions, also molecular complexes and binding, structure modification, subcellular localisation, and more
- Other class: utility
- EntityReference (ER) is a unique identifier
- Other class: interaction/control; e.g. conversion, direction of the conversion, left-right, stoichiometry, direct-indirect control, including subclasses for control; BUT: no rate constants, no rate laws
- Pathways are described, e.g. with a list of interactions, by a defined order, can control/be controlled, phenotype/outcome etc.
- Link to external resources and ontologies established
- BioPAX describes more static than dynamic situation; pathwaycommons.org: repository for pathways data validated in BioPAX format
- Challenge is to automatically integrate standards
- Difference exists between inconsistencies and mistakes (mistakes are based on wrong information or data)

SEEKING our way to better presentation of data and models from scientific investigations, using commons, standard formats, and semantic linking

Natalie Stanford

- SEEK has various levels of openness settings (fully public to fully private, and shades in between)
- Challenge: difference types of data sources and systems if work is done in large consortia
- Data in files can be ambiguous -> difficult to share data or reuse data
- Has influence on publications, discoveries etc.
- We need new ways of formatting, storing and sharing data
- SEEK = commons originally designed for centralizing information and assets for large consortia and projects
- SEEK contains various types of information
- Each user has their own profile, and data and models are uploaded to own profile or project etc.; full control of the person uploading the information
- SEEK works as aggregated asset manager
- SEEK uses ISA format; the ISA structure reflects an intuitive structure and storage of scientific findings
- SEEK also integrates with other tools, e.g. BioPortal, PubMed, openBIS, JWS, BioModels, SABIO
- FAIRDOM (www.fair-dom.org): open platform for upload of assets, linked with DOI
- Different standards for systems biology available; can be a barrier
- RightField: semantic annotation tool for data files; to generate templates for different types of assay data

Requirements for Systems Biology Standards in Medical Decision Making

Andreas Posch

presentation not recorded on request

- Topics of interest to Siemens: industry, energy, healthcare, infrastructures and cities
- In healthcare interest in decision-support models
- Limitations: sequence variants are not described unambiguously
- Use case: Integrated care platform for systems medicine.
- Requirements of systems biology standards in medical decision making
 - Challenges:
 - reduce complexity
 - tracking quality of parameters
 - standards for effective sharing & integration
 - PPPs and open innovation

Discussion:

- Question HW: Does Siemens have modelling in-house?
Answer AP: We provide and set up just the infrastructure; more a healthcare information system environment; not so much systems biology, but having access to such expertise would be of interest, especially in biomedical context
- Remark NLN on systems biology vs. systems medicine: because of the Smorgasbord in different national regulations around medical data etc., the bioinformatics infrastructure ELIXIR excluded the medical sector from its remit.

Synthetic Biology and Visualization Standards

The Systems Biology Graphical Notation (SBGN)

Falk Schreiber

- Motivation of SBGN: we have an ambiguity of representations of pathways; it was necessary to find a unified/standardised way to visualise pathways

- SBGN: 3 languages in one - process description map, relationship maps, activity flow maps
- Many tools supporting SBGN, linking to COMBINE and Harmony activities
- SBGN can be combined with SBO and other standards
- SBGN and SBML work together
- SBGN can visualise models produced in other standards
- Planning to integrate also SBOL
- Challenge: many different “worlds” of experimentalists exist, all with different requirements and background; it might be difficult to satisfy all in one approach; SBGN needs to be self-explanatory, if an extensive legend is needed to explain, the purpose of SBGN is lost

Discussion:

- Question: what is needed?
Answer FS: more engagement of industry and publishers, more participants to develop SBGN, funding
- PH: We could do with extensions to SBGN with icons that biologists are familiar with
FS: This is currently under discussion
PH: It would even be better if they were to be customisable.
FS: We are indeed discussing to be more flexible.
- Overall agreement that graphical representations and code sheet need to be both available.

The Synthetic Biology Open Language (SBOL)

Chris J. Myers

- Synbio potential uses:
 - Produce drugs and biofuels
 - Consume toxic waste
 - Destroy tumours
- Synbio extends genetic engineering by:
 - Standards
 - Abstraction
 - Decoupling
- A principle problem in synthetic biology is the reproducibility of experiments from publications -> need for a standard language -> enter SBOL
- Active participation of industry in SBOL
- SBOL (chair: Herbert Sauro) – standard symbols for biological entities (gene, ribosome, promoter, 5' overhang, etc.)
- SBOL has a data model part: describes the design of the actual DNA sequence, hierarchical composition of DNA components (similar to GenBank), multiple levels of hierarchy, allows to specify incomplete design
- Connects via ontology
- SBOL version 1.1: visual representation
- SBOL version 2.0: adds functional range; also gives hierarchy support for the design
- Synergies between SBOL and COMBINE; but avoid multiplication of standards -> leverage of existing standards
- Connect SBOL to SBML, BioPAX, repositories
- It should be easy for authors to put their results in standardised formats. Publishers should demand it (when possible). SBOL also tries to make publishing easier; reproducibility is a serious problem; SBOL is partnering with ACS Synthetic Biology (one of the major journals in synthetic biology); JBEI is a common repository, and the journal requires the deposit of the information in JBEI that supports SBOL

- Compliance testing is another challenge; Often standards get blamed for failures in workflows, while it is often the tools that fail. Tool developers should be well supported. We have to define what it means for a tool or workflows to support a standard

Discussion:

- Question: how could an initiative such as ISBE help?
Answer CJM: It would be desirable to have a single portal to find all tools etc.
- Moreover, support for semantics, as this is often absent from biological diagrams, hence making them ambiguous (e.g. two inhibitor signs on one process: AND? OR?)

General Discussion

Interfaces, Interoperability, Concerted actions, Standardisation bodies

1) Synopsis of the different existing initiatives

- Already well-discussed

2) How to bundle the efforts of all stakeholders?

- Stakeholder groups:
 - Standards developers
 - Research initiatives and industries using and applying the standards
 - AP: Sustainability of standards very important for industry (what will happen if a company decides to put SBML in one of its products after its funding has run out in 2016?)
 - Publishers & journals
 - TL: Community determines and implements standards. Applying the standards in publishing can become policy once a standard becomes dominant. Publishers can then help to enforce. Myself, as a publisher, I would like to be aware when and where key standards discussions take place to attend (maybe just as observer). Publishers can support to raise awareness for standards.
 - Publishing a paper about standards is rewarding; with expected high citation rates this is also attractive for publishers.
 - The personal contact to the publishers is very important.
 - There must be a clear illustration of the benefit to raise interest in new standards.
 - CJM: Publishing standards are also key to science reproducibility. Today we face the situation that the reproducibility of science is decreasing; standards are very important to reverse this situation.
 - There has been a meeting with most of the large scientific publishers (30-40 chief editors convened, workshop on the reproducibility of science); they agreed on various aspects of how standards are to be integrated into the publishing process.
 - Question MJM: How often and to what extent do different publishers work together in establishing publishing standards? Do they do so in an active or reactive fashion?
Answer TL: Although it is taken very seriously, unfortunately it does not happen very often. Also in this light it would be useful if publishers were kept informed on standards activities and sometimes invited by standards communities
 - Consensus that funders could be the most potent drivers towards implementation of standards
 - Standardisation bodies (e.g. ISO, CEN, WC3)

- Also standardisation bodies could provide support for the standardisation process.
- Industry
 - For industry it is very important to be the first (to create and/or) implement a standard. For industry it is key to have up-to-date knowledge.
- Scientific society as a whole & open discussion
 - Question is who is the user; in data generation standards are much more important for biologists. Also for data exchange it is very important to have standards.
 - Are users willing to share data? Overall impression is yes, nowadays it become much more important to share data.
 - AP: From big company perspective, this could be important to drive the decision to take up a certain standard.
 - Australian Data Initiative represents an inter-government initiative for data exchange. Could this be a model for Europe as well?
 - How can we ensure sustainability of standards? Who could be interested to invest? Funding from public institutions is scarce for this field; industry is interested, but there is an overlap of standards and approaches, which makes it difficult for industry to decide where to invest and which standard will survive and be sustainable?
 - MH: We need a flowchart to guide people in helping them choose the standard that they might need/want to use.
 - Question MG: Should there be an effort, like for instance an international society, to bring people together?
PH: Yes, but this could be done through initiatives like COMBINE (for modelling) and VPH (for interfacing with clinics).
 - NLN: Users don't use standards. Tool developers do. They need to make good tools. Then the users will use those tools.
 - TL: Not fully true, since experimental scientists use experimental standards, and subsequent data standards. There is a much broader community beyond modelling etc. Awareness among experimentalists about data standards is not always high. But they seem not unwilling to work with them once they know.
 - PH: Funding agencies are the key. Industry is not going to develop them (they will follow), and publishers cannot afford it.
 - Remark Australian funder: we do not fund standards development.
 - NLN: We should not talk about standards then
 - MJM: As MH already mentioned before, there is no academic career path for standards development, neither for the software and tools development to make them successful. Can we create a new career path? And if yes, do we need an institution to promote this? Consensus that this would be necessary.

3. ISBE-CASyM joint Meeting on Education and Training

Date:

25 September 2014

Venue:

Villa del Grumello – Centro di Cultura Scientifica “A. Volta”
Via per Cernobbio 11, 22100 Como, Italy

Participants:

Jure Acimovic (JA)	ISBE + CASyM
Lilia Alberghina (LA)	SysBio (Italy) + ISBE (associated)
Damjana Rozman (DR)	ISBE + CASyM
Heide Marie Hess (HMH)	ERASysAPP; SystemsX.ch
Marc Kirschner (MK)	CASyM
Walter Kolch (WK)	ISBE + CASyM
Gregor Lorbek (GL)	ISBE + CASyM
Martijn J. Moné (MJM)	ISBE
Hans Westerhoff (HW)	ISBE + CASyM (associated)

Notes and Actions Points of the Meeting

- 1) It was agreed that ISBE, CASyM and ERASysAPP work in collaboration.
- 2) ISBE business case is to include a paragraph on CASyM, positioning the medical aspect
- 3) Write a joint position paper (white paper) on training and business case. It should be accessible and attractive.
- 4) Broaden the collaboration through EMTRAIN
 - Identify ISBE and CASyM person to keep up to date with EMTRAIN
- 5) Look together at what ERA-NET calls are of interest to this end. HW and HMH will provide the outline. Assess what courses would be funded by ERA-NET
- 6) ERASysAPP project ends on December 2015. Sustainability of ERASysAPP outcomes: there was consensus that it would be a good resolution if ISBE were to ingest the resulting data and knowledge for their continuing accessibility.
- 7) European systems biology training infrastructure
 - A set off connected courses across Europe
 - Collect existing courses (not depending on grant application)
 - Defining the most relevant courses for systems medicine
 - Focus on providing information on training rather than providing the courses
 - Identify groups that have a high reputation in systems biology and are willing to train
 - CASyM partners are to provide medical input
 - ISBE acts as a technical operator
 - UL will review books with Systems Biology in the title (Springer)

- 8) Under D10.4, ISBE will have a pilot systems biology / systems medicine course, which will most probably be held in Slovenia early July 2015
- A list of 2014-2015 systems biology / systems medicine courses (to not overlap with new ones):
 - Stoichiometric and Kinetic Modelling of Biochemical Networks (20 participants)
October 6-10, 2014, Larnaca, Cyprus
 - Systems Pharmacology
January 29-30, 2015, Amsterdam, The Netherlands
 - Data Integration in the Life Sciences (max. 20 participants)
February 2-6, 2015, Lorentz Center Leiden, The Netherlands
 - 7th International Practical Course in Systems Biology
June 1-12, 2015, Göteborg, Sweden
 - Advanced Summer in Systems Medicine
June, 22-26, 2014, Stockholm, Sweden

Shorthand of the business case for SB

Melbourne, 15 September 2014

Infrastructure Systems Biology Europe (ISBE)

For discussion at the ICSB2014 in Melbourne

Date/Time: 15-September-2014 Monday/ 7pm

Venue:

Restaurant Silks

Level 1, Crown Towers (Crown Hotel)

8 Whiteman Street, Southbank, Melbourne, Australia

Attendees

Peter Hunter

Mike Hucka

Stefan Hohmann

Martijn Moné

Hans Westerhoff

Garry Corthals

Thomas Lemberger

Hiroaki Kitano

Nicolas Le Novère

Babette Regierer

Mission

- To establish and provide access to an integrated, distributed infrastructure of state-of-the-art facilities for systems biology across Europe
- To enable European life scientists from all sectors to solve complex biological problems with a systems-wide perspective

Further information:
www.isbe.eu

Join the community:
community.isbe.eu

Timeline

Preparatory Phase Objectives:

- Identification of existing activities and consultation with stakeholders regarding the technical requirements of the infrastructure
- A proposal outlining the recommendations for the technical specifications of the physical infrastructure, required technologies and access policies
- Development and negotiation of a business plan and sustainable funding model for the construction and operational phase of ISBE

ISBE offers

**Access to
data + expertise
in a network
for
systems biology
approaches**

...and Training:

Access to web-based training
tools and programmes

We offer an outline of a Systems Biology Research Infrastructure

HOW WILL ISBE WORK?

CONFIDENTIAL

Shorthand of the business case for

Infrastructure Systems Biology Europe (ISBE)

For discussion at the ICSB2014 in Melbourne

Date/Time: 15-September-2014 Monday/ 7pm

Venue:

Restaurant Silks

Level 1, Crown Towers (Crown Hotel)

8 Whiteman Street, Southbank, Melbourne, Australia

Invitees

Peter Hunter

Mike Hucka

Stefan Hohmann

Martijn Moné

Hans Westerhoff

Garry Corthals

Thomas Lemberger

Hiroaki Kitano

Nicolas Le Novère

Babette Regierer

Pamela Silver

Marc Wilkins

What we asked...

- Please comment on whether this is an attractive outline of a Systems Biology Research Infrastructure

Infrastructure Systems Biology Europe (ISBE)

Business case

Summary in pictures

Systems biology works across multiple scales and disciplines

from Hunter P, Robbins P & Noble D (2002). *The IUPS human physiome project*. European Journal of Physiology **445**, 1-9.

Systems biology continuously integrates data through modelling and renewed experimentation

How ISBE will address current challenges in systems biology

Current issues in the systems biology process

The ISBE solutions

Building on national strengths

Links with other ESFRIs

Governance

Funding

ISBE Infrastructure
for Systems Biology
Europe

Central funding by Member States

- ◆ European Legal identity — ERIC.
- ◆ Supports Standing bodies and Central ISBE Office
- ◆ Hosted at existing Centres of Excellence

National Funding for National Systems Biology Centres (NSBCs)

- ◆ National legal entities at existing Centres of Excellence
- ◆ Provides Services and resources.

Establishing ISBE

ISBE timeline (2014 - 2018)

Infrastructure Systems Biology Europe (ISBE)

Business case

The document you saw
Summary in words

ISBE Vision

To create a pan-European infrastructure for systems biology that will facilitate the use of model-driven approaches to understand complex biological systems in a way that enables their function to be altered in a rational and predictive way. This will provide the tools and resources necessary for researchers in academia and industry to address current and future challenges in healthcare, the bio-economy and the sustainable environment, enhancing the European economy and the well-being of its citizens.

ISBE Mission

To construct and manage a distributed infrastructure of interconnected systems biology resources and services, co-ordinated at a national and European level. This will facilitate model-driven, predictive biology and its application to the understanding of biological function from a multi-discipline and multi-scale perspective by providing:

- the development and adoption of community standards and best practices for the generation and curation of data and models
- effective stewardship of model-related data and development of relevant models, allowing their ongoing use by multiple researchers
- community access to interoperable models, data, biological maps and tools enhancing systems biology education and training at multiple levels

RAISON D'ETRE OF BUSINESS CASE

The business case document:

SHOULD BUT DOES IT?

- outlines steps for how the creation of ISBE will significantly improve economic growth (i.e. support for industry and the creation of jobs) for the EU
- is mainly aimed at Funders, and is in anticipation of the more detailed Business plan, to be produced in July 2015
- details the importance of SB to the bio economy and how ISBE addresses these issues.
- expands on the clear distinction between ISBE as an infrastructure, rather than a network.
- explains the unique contribution that ISBE can make and how it fits with the other ESFRI infrastructures (particularly the fit with ELIXIR).

ISBE model structure

Two layer hub and spoke model:

- European level
 - the Central ISBE Office
- National level
 - ‘hub’= a leading university which would host the national coordinating centre (nSBC)
 - spokes = other universities or research institutes which will contribute to ISBE. (Only some countries will be able to provide expertise and facilities in all SB aspects)

SECTION 1

Introduction announcing what the business case will highlight...

SECTION	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The strong and diverse community structure within systems biology research
4&5	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Needs for making systems biology approaches more easily accessible in academia, clinical research and industry
6&7	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The resources, services and associated expertise and the physical structure of the infrastructure and its centres that ISBE should offer
8	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The way ISBE will develop training resources, courses and workshops, and support systems biology education
9&10	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The governance, legal and financial aspects of the infrastructure
11	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The way the ISBE infrastructure will be rolled out in the forthcoming years

SECTION 2

Systems biology needs

- Community-driven technical standards and standard operating procedures (SOPs)
- Tight cooperation between different disciplines
- Since the mathematical and computational background of life scientists is often limited, focussed education and training programmes are essential to broadly implement systems biology approaches in the life sciences

SECTION 3

Aims of ISBE: Researchers in systems biology need infrastructure that supports the following

- Diverse data and model exchange in a standardised manner that is accessible and understandable between all partners
- Access to both data and models to ensure that groups working primarily in experimental or computational work can progress the systems biology research life-cycle without the need for additional expertise within their group
- Development of software that facilitates to model biological data
- Future-proof operational needs of systems biology
- Development and dissemination of best practice in systems biology training and education at all levels
- Broad range of users: academia, hospitals and clinics and industry
- Four tightly linked domains: modelling, standardisation, stewardship and data generation

SECTION 4

Network of national Systems Biology Centres

- SBE will form an integrated but distributed European network of national Systems Biology Centres with overlapping and complementary expertise
- Easy access for ISBE users to the infrastructure either web-based or physical
- ISBE will set out the eligibility criteria and the process for selection that apply to all candidate ISBE nSBCs

SECTION 5

Services, resources and tools

- **Services**
 - Consultancy and contract activities
 - Training , education and outreach
- **Resources**
 - Tools, data, maps and models
 - Community standards and SOPs
 - Repositoryies and archives (long-term storage and curation of models, and the data, tools and protocols)
- **Community activities**
 - Workshops, conferences and training courses

SECTION 6

Education and training

- Support of postgraduate education in systems biology through development of core curricula
- Competency based short courses for users
- SBC staff training in collaboration with other RIs
- Up-to-date database of systems biology courses, workshops and conferences
- Customised training for industry

SECTION 7

Cooperation with other life science research infrastructures and organisations

- Cooperate and tune activities and services with other research infrastructures (RIs)
- ISBE actively participates in the Horizon 2020 INFRADEV-4 proposal that aims at harmonising and synergising the European RIs
- ISBE is actively engaging with RIs in medical, marine and microbial research, as well tackling cross-cutting issues relating to data, resources and technologies

SECTION 8

Legal structure and governance

- Robust and effective financial, legal and governance structure that supports efficient operations and strategic planning
- ERIC as its long-term legal personality

The CIO is to:

- Employ ISBE director and administrative staff that will support the standing bodies, and operations across all NSBCs.
- Operate legal agreements with each of the NSBCs, as well as being the legal body for agreements with other Research Infrastructures, including other ESFRIs
- Standing bodies that will ensure:
 - Involvement of funders and scientists from member states in the overarching governing board
 - internal technical coordination and strategic planning
 - External expert advice from Industry, users and other stakeholders
 - Due consideration of ethical issues

SECTION 9

Finance

- ISBE will increase value for money and return on existing national systems biology investments by utilising national subscriptions from those member states hosting nSBCs, to support the Central ISBE Office operational budget.
- Operating costs for national SBCs will be met through existing national funding mechanisms, i.e. through existing competitive processes, and/or strategic resourcing of host institutions.
- ISBE's five years financial plan will ensure clarity and longer-term financial planning and enable improved sustainability of services.
- CIO: ~€101k-in year 1 to €520k in year 5. This will coordinate roughly €7.3M of national investments per annum.
- ISBE established once at least 5 member states and associated nSBCs have agreed to join,

SECTION 10

Building ISBE – *action plan*

- **Preparatory phase (until July 2015)**
 - MoU, with identified support from signatory states
 - Nominations for candidate NSBCs
 - CIO identified

- **Interim phase (2015-17)**
 - Appoint the director
 - Establish and operate the interim bodies
 - Further nominations of candidate NSBCs
 - Negotiation of the ERIC agreement will be concluded

- **Established following 5 signatories to the ERIC (expected by end of 2017)**
 - Start of the first 4-5 year financial operational, and funding cycle.
 - Standing boards established
 - legal agreements with NBSCs and other ESFRIs.
 - ISBE will continue to consult stakeholders on their needs across all phases

- **ISBE is already developing a risk management process for all phases, including a detailed risk register and KPIs**

Further suggestions

- ?

ISBE Infrastructure
for Systems Biology
Europe

ISBE: Infrastructure for Systems Biology – Europe

a research infrastructure to make systems biology big and integrative

ICSB 2014 – Melbourne, Australia | September 18, 2014

*NormSys/ISBE Workshop “Standards for Data and Model Exchange
in Systems Biology”*

www.isbe.eu

ESFRI

- Project on the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) roadmap – set to have a large impact on the life science community across Europe
- The preparatory phase of ISBE started in August 2012 and is funded for three years under FP7 as one of 13 ESFRI projects in the field of Biological and Medical Sciences
- Infrastructures serve long-term needs of the European research communities

Timeline ISBE

Mission ISBE

To establish and enable access to an integrated, distributed infrastructure of state-of-the-art resources and expertise for systems biology across Europe, with a view to transforming our understanding of the life sciences, human health and the environment.

To this end, create a solid pan-European technological, intellectual and training basis and provide services **allowing researchers in academia and industry** to:

- **Collect, analyse and process datasets** for integration into effective models
- **Build predictive models** that give insight into the functioning of biological systems
- Access a **platform from which to launch large-scale integrative projects** of great scientific and societal impact

Vision

- Provide a **single point of entry** for systems biology
- **Make data, models, maps and tools available** for the broad scientific community
- Support implementation of community-driven **standards and SOPs**
- Enable European life scientists to tackle complex biological problems from a systems perspective, by providing **access to hubs of technological excellence and expertise in systems biology**
- **Offer the best** multidisciplinary training, expertise, model and data repositories, and modelling facilities

Vision

- Enable small projects and large community efforts by **connecting the expertise and resources** of multiple centres of systems biology expertise and training across Europe
- Drive understanding of biological functioning of biological systems at many scales – from **molecules to cells to whole organisms and ecosystems**
- Drive **exploitation** of this knowledge for applications in systems medicine, bio-industries, agriculture, and the environment.

Why ISBE?

Why do we need an infrastructure for systems biology?

- Systems biology requires a combination of **resources and expertise** that is generally **not present at one location** (or even within a single country)
- To make use of existing knowledge, methodologies, facilities, and expertise, and to **enable re-use of biological data and models**

Scientific connections

Modelling-driven; integration-centric

Why ISBE?

How will ISBE provide services to the scientific community?

- Provide **easy and rapid access** through several preferred access policies
- **Support** scientists in developing **efficient and cost-effective systems biology project**
- Support (**small or large**, national or international) systems biology projects
- Support **standards** that allow the **re-use of data, models, maps and tools**
- Provide **training and education**
- Provide a **portfolio of services**, ranging from e.g. consultancy to individual researchers up to long-term contracts with large international research consortia and with industry

Systems biology structured in connected centres throughout Europe

- Single point of entry for users (academia and industry)
- Model-driven & integration centric focus
- Supporting the full systems biology cycle
- Research and training
- Access to data, models, maps and tools
- Standards and SOPs
- Expertise in a wide range of computational modelling approaches – integrating diverse datasets into quantitative and predictive models
- Data storage, curation and analysis of SB relevant datasets. Standards and SOPs for data generation.
- Multiscale systems biology: molecules – cells – tissues – organs – physiology – ecosystems
- Platform to launch small and large-scale research programmes (e.g. virtual organisms)

Stewardship sources

different funding models – national/international investments

Open – Closed | Commercial - Non-commercial | Secure – Public

Client Data/models generated by projects supported/hosted by ISBE infrastructure & services.
Hosting, standards, platforms

Born SysBio

ISBE ISBE public data/models resources, primary responsibility for stewarding and sustaining
Hosting, standards, interop, services

Made SysBio

Other RIs Data generated or stewarded by other RIs, e.g. ELIXIR
Ingest, standards, interop, services

Stewardship

Minimal Conventions

- ISBE will provide conventions that enable data interoperability and stewardship and compliance against data and metadata standards, policies and practices
- Proposal – the minimal “hourglass” approach, the same as that which underpins the internet, the web and other robust, heterogeneous yet interoperable infrastructures.

Why is stewardship important for ISBE / Systems Biology?

- Broker between experimentalists and modellers
 - Definition of **interfaces** between data, metadata and models
 - Definition of **standards and formats** to fit together data and models
 - Consulting of experimentalists and modellers on needs for **storage**
 - **Transferring** needs of modellers to experimentalists (and vice versa)
- Channelling of data flow within and across projects
 - Ensuring data and model **consistency**
 - **Harmonising** the description and composition of (meta-)data/models
- Agent for community standardisation efforts
- Curation of data and models
 - Ensuring **consistency and high quality** of data and models
 - Ensuring **coherence across** the systems biology **community**

Connections

Different types of scientific connections

- A set of **connections between core systems biology nodes**, effectively enabling an expertise centre that may be geographically distributed (yet providing a **single point of entry** for users)
- **Connections between systems biology centres of different complementary expertise** (e.g. different modelling methodologies) enabling their integration when addressing a certain systems biology problem
- Enable users to do effective systems biology through **access to training and education** (courses, eLearning)

ISBE nodes and connections

Reinforcement by re-use of output

Connections vision

Connecting data, models and expertise

- ISBE as driver of (a) visionary project(s) with great scientific and societal impact
- Virtual maize, virtual yeast, virtual human – multiscale
- Can draw from the same resources

Connections

- ISBE centres as part of an interconnected **platform from which to launch integrative visionary projects with great scientific and societal impact**, as well as the smaller projects that make important sub-models and resolve key parameters under relevant conditions
- Because systems biology is synergy of modelling, experimentation, data processing, etc., ISBE should be a network of systems biology expertise centres organized to **operate as a dynamic, flexible and scalable infrastructure**
- **Data stewardship** in a model-driven fashion, providing access to **model-ready data**.

ISBE will make
best use of
synergies

with other European
infrastructures
to link diverse data-sets
through systems biology
modelling

Bioinformatics

Imaging

Biobanking

Clinical Research

Marine Biology

Structural Biology

Translational Medicine

INFRAFRONTIER
Mouse Models

Chemical Biology

Microorganisms

Community web-site

community.isbe.eu

ISBE

ISBE project web-site

- ISBE mailing list
- Survey
- Direct email contact
- Make your Institution an associate partner

isbe.eu

ISBE Infrastructure
for Systems Biology
Europe

Thank you!

Present here:

HITS GmbH Heidelberg
Martin Golebiewski

Wageningen University
Babette Regierer

Univ. of Manchester
Natalie Stanford

VU University Amsterdam
Martijn Moné (m.j.mone@vu.nl)
Hans Westerhoff

www.isbe.eu

Model-driven data management

Hans V. Westerhoff, and friends

*Amsterdam Institute for Molecules, Medicines and Systems, VU University
Amsterdam*

*Synthetic Systems Biology, SILS, the University of Amsterdam
Manchester Centre for Integrative Systems Biology, University of Manchester*

My topics

**Data management for systems biology/medicine
should be different:**

Data need to be integrated:

Silicon/virtual organisms:

Human metabolic map:

Silicon cell models:

Further integration:

Science greatest challenges

Woman on Mars?

Higgs boson?

Human genome sequence?

To understand how the human body works

To cure multifactorial disease

**Man on the moon, human
genome sequence, Higgs boson,
these great challenges were
addressed by BIG SCIENCE
not by a cottage industry, hence:**

**We need to *organize* Systems
BioMedicine**

Understanding the human through a cottage industry

In French

In English

In Slovenian

In German

In Japanese

In Chinese

We need to organize

**(not to define everything, but to
define all interfacing)**

Background

The problem

- **Data explosion** on components
- **Implosion of understanding** (of how dynamic interactions lead to robust function)
- **Individual research groups** cannot handle it all:
 - Technical limitations
 - Limited access to expertise and equipment
 - Foreign expertises are needed (e.g. modelling for experimentalists)

- **We seem to be stuck: data but no understanding**

- **At the same time systems medicine is faced with virtually insurmountable**

challenges

- **Which do require everyone to be on (the same) board**

ISBE Infrastructure
for Systems Biology
Europe

The good news:
Thanks to **Systems Biology** we
now understand why we got stuck

**Each of us was looking at
his favourite molecule
and needed no data sharing**

ISBE Infrastructure
for Systems Biology
Europe

**Systems Biology has shown that
these multifactorial diseases are**

Networking diseases

ISBE Infrastructure
for Systems Biology
Europe

Hence:

We should not be looking at individual molecules but at networks

We should not store data as individual molecules but as dynamic networks

My topics

Data management for systems biology/medicine
should be different: **network accommodating**

Data need to be integrated:

Silicon/virtual organisms:

Human metabolic map:

Silicon cell models:

Further integration:

However.....

**If we have to understand large
networks:**

**We depend even more on
understanding and integrating large
data sets and on integrating scientists**

metabolomics

proteomics

transcriptomics

genomics

The data are available: we can know almost all molecules and functions: **BIG DATA**

structural biology

biochemistry

biophysics

biology

physiology

All DNA

All RNA

All proteins

All metabolites

metabolomics

prot

structural biology

biophysics

biochemistry

biology

physiology

We need to integrate

metabolomics

proteomics

transcriptomics

genomics

structural biology

biochemistry

biophysics

biology

My topics

Data management for systems biology/medicine
should be different: **network accommodating**

Data need to be integrated: **'organically'**

Silicon/virtual organisms:

Human metabolic map:

Silicon cell models:

Further integration:

Data integration, but how?

- **Put data together in replica model:**
 - Virtual organism
- **Such a computer replica model:**
 - Stores the data (or pointers to) where they belong organically
 - Integrates them automatically
 - Makes them predictive

The virtual twin – a “person simulator”

But.....the whole organism

seems to be too complex.....

My topics

Data management for systems biology/medicine
should be different: **network accommodating**

Data need to be integrated: **'organically'**

Silicon/virtual organisms: **as integrators**

Human metabolic map:

Silicon cell models:

Further integration:

Many people still say that data integration is impossible and stick with data collection and with putting the data into non-integrative databases

....

But in some clever ways and cases, data integration *has* been happening

The Human global metabolic map

nature biotechnology

THE SCIENCE AND BUSINESS OF BIOTECHNOLOGY

NBT: 3 March 2013

A community-driven global reconstruction of human metabolism

Ines Thiele^{1,2,37}, Neil Swainston^{3,4,37}, Ronan M T Fleming^{1,5}, Andreas Hoppe⁶, Swagatika Sahoo¹, Maike K Aurich¹, Hulda Haraldsdottir¹, Monica L Mo⁷, Ottar Rolfsson¹, Miranda D Stobbe^{8,9}, Stefan G Thorleifsson¹, Rasmus Agren¹⁰, Christian Bölling⁶, Sergio Bordel¹⁰, Arvind K Chavali¹¹, Paul Dobson¹², Warwick B Dunn^{3,13}, Lukas Endler¹⁴, David Hala¹⁵, Michael Hucka¹⁶, Duncan Hull⁴, Daniel Jameson^{3,4}, Neema Jamshidi⁷, Jon J Jonsson⁵, Nick Judy¹⁷, Sarah Keating¹⁷, Intawat Nookaew¹⁰, Nicolas Le Novère^{17,18}, Naglis Malys^{3,19,20}, Alexander Mazein²¹, Jason A Papin¹¹, Nathan D Price²², Evgeni Selkov, Sr²³, Martin I Sigurdsson¹, Evangelos Simeonidis^{22,24}, Nikolaus Sonnenschein²⁵, Kieran Smallbone^{3,26}, Anatoly Sorokin^{21,27}, Johannes H G M van Beek²⁸⁻³⁰, Dieter Weichart^{3,31}, Igor Goryanin^{21,32}, Jens Nielsen¹⁰, Hans V Westerhoff^{3,28,33,34}, Douglas B Kell^{3,35}, Pedro Mendes^{3,4,36} & Bernhard Ø Palsson^{1,7}

Multiple models of human metabolism have been reconstructed, but each represents only a subset of our knowledge. Here we describe Recon 2, a community-driven, consensus 'metabolic reconstruction', which is the most comprehensive representation of human metabolism that is applicable to computational modeling. Compared with its predecessors, the reconstruction has improved topological and functional features, including ~2× more reactions and ~1.7× more unique metabolites. Using Recon 2 we predicted changes in metabolite biomarkers for 49 inborn errors of metabolism with 77% accuracy when compared to experimental data. Mapping metabolomic data and drug information onto Recon 2 demonstrates its potential for integrating and analyzing diverse data types. Using protein expression data, we automatically generated a compendium of 65 cell type-specific models, providing a basis for manual curation or investigation of cell-specific metabolic properties. Recon 2 will facilitate many future biomedical studies and is freely available at <http://humanmetabolism.org/>.

An understanding of metabolism is fundamental to comprehending the phenotypic behavior of all living organisms, including humans, where metabolism is integral to health and is involved in much of human disease. High quality, genome-scale 'metabolic reconstructions' are at the heart of bottom-up systems biology analyses and represent the entire network of metabolic reactions that a given organism is known to exhibit¹. The metabolic-network reconstruction procedure

is now well-established² and has been applied to a growing number of model organisms³. Metabolic reconstructions allow for the conversion of biological knowledge into a mathematical format and the subsequent computation of physiological states^{1,4,5} to address a variety of scientific and applied questions^{3,6}. Reconstructions enable network-wide mechanistic investigations of the genotype-phenotype relationship. A high-quality reconstruction of the metabolic network is thus

Our perspective: Start where the action is Then treat the rest as accessory

This is the library

This is the regulatory level

This is the work floor of the cell:
The metabolic level

Food for thought

Metabolism:

A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C

We could at least first try to annotate all metabolic genes by function i.e. by the reaction their enzymes catalyze

We could at least first try to annotate the metabolic genes by function i.e. by the reaction their enzymes catalyze

annotate the metabolic genes by function i.e. by the reaction their enzymes catalyze and then order them by metabolite

We obtained the **genome wide metabolic map**, i.e. all the network can make from any food

**The human metabolic map is a
replica model that**

Stores data/Organizes data

Integrates data

Makes data predictive

Example: Human genome wide map

Example of Data Stewardship

- All metabolic genes were integrated into metabolic maps
- The different metabolic maps were integrated
- We now agree on how we make ourselves!

The Human global metabolic map

Inborn errors of metabolism and diet: network analysis possible now

nature biotechnology NBT: 3 March 2013
THE VOICES AND BUSINESS OF BIOTECHNOLOGY

A community-driven global reconstruction of human metabolism

Joost Thiele^{1,2,3*}, Neil Swainston^{1,4,5*}, Ronan M. F. Fleming^{1,6*}, Andreas Hoppe⁷, Evangelia Ianiro⁸, Marko K. Aantaa⁹, Hilde Haralabidou¹⁰, Susana E. Mei¹¹, Oliver Bollmann¹², Miriam D. Hoshida¹³, Stefan G. Theofanis¹⁴, Ramesh Aggar¹⁵, Christian Billing¹⁶, Sergio Basso¹⁷, Arvid K. Chavakis¹⁸, Paul Dobson¹⁹, Warwick B. Dunn²⁰, Lukas Endler²¹, David Hale²², Michael Huska²³, Duncan Hall²⁴, Daniel Junemann²⁵, Nuno Justiz²⁶, Jose J. Juarez²⁷, Nick Jerry²⁸, Sarah Keating²⁹, Jeroen Kokkawa³⁰, Nicolas Le Novre³¹, Nigita Malya³², Alexander Mavrou³³, Jason A. Payne³⁴, Nathan D. Price³⁵, Egorii Selkov³⁶, Martin J. Signorini³⁷, Evangelos Stamatidis³⁸, Nikolaos Sotiriou³⁹, Kieran Smallbone⁴⁰, Alexander Soudki⁴¹, Johannes H. G. M. van Schaik⁴², Dorian Suckling⁴³, Igor G. Usachev⁴⁴, Jero Nijssen⁴⁵, Hans V. Westerhoff^{46,47,48,49}, Douglas B. Kell⁵⁰, Pedro Mendes^{51,52} & Bernhard O. Palsson⁵³

Multiple models of human metabolism have been reconstructed, but each represents only a subset of our knowledge. Here we describe Reactome 2, a community-driven, consensus 'metabolic reconstruction', which is the most comprehensive representation of human metabolism that is applicable to computational modeling. Compared with its predecessor, the reconstruction has improved topological and functional features, including 26 new reactions and 3.2-fold more enzyme metabolites. Using Reactome 2 we predicted changes to metabolite fluxes for 49 dietary items of metabolism with 77% accuracy when compared to experimental data. Mapping metabolomic data and drug information onto Reactome 2 demonstrates its potential for integrating and analyzing diverse data types. Using protein expression data, we automatically generated a compendium of 65 cell-type-specific models, providing a basis for manual curatorial or investigation of cell-specific metabolic properties. Reactome 2 will facilitate many future biomedical studies and is freely available at <http://www.reactome.org>.

An understanding of metabolism is fundamental to comprehending the phenotype behavior of all living organisms, including humans, where metabolism is integral to health and is involved in such of human disease. High-quality genome-wide 'metabolic reconstructions' are at the heart of systems biology analyses and represent the entire network of metabolic reactions that a given organism is known to utilize. The metabolic network reconstruction procedure is now well-established and has been applied to a growing number of model organisms, including bacteria. The combination of biological knowledge into a mathematical format and the subsequent comparison of phenotypic data^{1,2} to address a variety of scientific and applied questions^{3,4} has become an essential, wide-reaching investigation of the genotype-phenotype relationship. A high-quality reconstruction of the metabolic network, in this

Volkskrant: 4 March 2013

de Volkskrant

Diët vervangt medicijn

Diet replaces medicine

My topics

Data management for systems biology/medicine
should be different: **network accommodating**

Data need to be integrated: **'organically'**

Silicon/virtual organisms: **as integrators**

Human metabolic map: **successful example of
such (static) data integration**

Silicon cell models:

Further integration:

And the glutathione dynamic map is an example of storing, organizing and integrating dynamic data and making those dynamically predictive

My topics

Data management for systems biology/medicine should be different: **network accommodating**

Data need to be integrated: **'organically'**

Silicon/virtual organisms: **as integrators**

Human metabolic map: **successful example of such (static) data integration**

Silicon cell models: **examples of such dynamic integrators (human glutathione, yeast, *T brucei*, erythrocyte, *E. coli* N..)**

Further integration:

Integration into each virtual organism

Connections – Nodes (or node collectives)

Integration into each virtual organism

Reinforcement by output

The virtual/silicon human

More effective and more affordable life sciences

To repeat at all scales; molecules to body

My topics

Data management for systems biology/medicine should be different: **network accommodating**

Data need to be integrated: **'organically'**

Silicon/virtual organisms: **as integrators**

Human metabolic map: **successful example of such (static) data integration**

Silicon cell models: **examples of such dynamic integrators (human glutathione, yeast, *T brucei*, erythrocyte, *E. coli* N..)**

Further integration: **associate building blocks**